

A measurement framework to assess software maturity models

Over the past few years, several maturity models have emerged, aiming to guide organizations in improving their processes and achieving higher levels of maturity. With every developed maturity model, researchers intend to collect varied viewpoints and insights from experts in the field. This approach aims to enhance the model with a comprehensive spectrum of knowledge and experiences. However, this process can be quite burdensome, requiring significant time and effort. Therefore, we propose the attached assessment and measurement framework for software maturity models which can be incredibly useful as it offers a structured approach to evaluating and quantifying the effectiveness, applicability, and impact of software maturity models within specific domains. Addressing this is essential for establishing a unified and comprehensive understanding of software maturity models, ensuring that these models are developed for specific contexts and rigorously assessed and validated across a range of criteria for broader applicability and impact.

**This survey will take 10 minutes of your valuable time and it will be used solely for research purposes. Answers are anonymized and your identity will not be revealed under any circumstances.

Demographics

* Current Role:

- Academic Researcher
- Project Manager
- Software Engineer
- PhD candidate
- Other

* Years of Experience in Software Assessment or Process Improvement:

- Less than 3 years
- 3 to 5 years
- 6 to 10 years

More than 10 years

Framework Ease of use

* The framework is logically structured and understandable by academic researchers and industry practitioners.

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neutral

Agree

Strongly agree

* All the criteria in the framework are self explanatory and requires no further clarification.

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neutral

Agree

Strongly agree

* The framework is easy to learn, enabling individuals with varying levels of expertise in software maturity models to utilize it effectively.

Strongly disagree

Disagree

- Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
-

* Some kind of training is necessary for the utilization of this framework.

- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
-

The framework structure

* The framework is thorough and considers all critical elements vital for assessing software maturity models.

- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
-

* The assessment process defined by the framework is time efficient and resource conservative.

- Strongly disagree

- Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
-

Assessment

* The framework provides precise and reliable indicators for assessing the quality of software maturity models.

- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
-

* The framework can identify areas of weakness and the areas of strength in a software maturity model.

- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
-

User Satisfaction

* I recommend this framework to colleagues and industry peers as a reliable tool for evaluating software maturity models?

- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
-

* The framework is applicable across diverse software development contexts and organizational sizes?

- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
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